

Infrastructure Access Report

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User-Project: AWRA-ONCE

Advanced wind resource assessments in offshore,
nearshore and coastal environments

University College Cork

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ABOUT MARINET

MARINET (Marine Renewables Infrastructure Network for emerging Energy Technologies) is an EC-funded network of research centres and organisations that are working together to accelerate the development of marine renewable energy - wave, tidal & offshore-wind. The initiative is funded through the EC's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) and runs for four years until 2015. The network of 29 partners with 42 specialist marine research facilities is spread across 11 EU countries and 1 International Cooperation Partner Country (Brazil).

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Partners

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ABOUT THIS REPORT

One of the requirements of the EC in enabling a user group to benefit from free-of-charge access to an infrastructure is that the user group must be entitled to disseminate the foreground (information and results) that they have generated under the project in order to progress the state-of-the-art of the sector. Notwithstanding this, the EC also state that dissemination activities shall be compatible with the protection of intellectual property rights, confidentiality obligations and the legitimate interests of the owner(s) of the foreground.

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- progress the state-of-the-art
- publicise resulting progress made for the technology/industry
- provide evidence of progress made along the Structured Development Plan
- provide due diligence material for potential future investment and financing
- share lessons learned
- avoid potential future replication by others
- provide opportunities for future collaboration
- etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The project focussed on improvements in offshore wind resource assessment. A model of the vertical profile of horizontal wind speeds is required in order to estimate wind resources at the rotor heights of proposed turbines. The specific goals were to (i) identify the best existing data sources and methods to incorporate atmospheric stability into vertical wind profile models and (ii) make recommendations for future offshore wind prospecting campaigns in order to adequately represent the effects of atmospheric stability.

The coastal wind speed data and related support obtained from NTNU allowed us to validate atmospheric stability corrections at a coastal site with a long marine fetch in several wind sectors. This allowed us to test the applicability of methodologies developed at offshore sites. The bulk correction method using sea surface roughness and temperatures performed well for the overseas fetch sector. The diabatic profile improved the vertical wind profile prediction in comparison to the neutral profile suggesting that the wind flow regime is predominantly influenced by the marine boundary layer. The air methods also showed potential to calculate the stability, although a difficulty arose from the use of the 25m temperature readings which appeared to cause errors. Possible impacts include improved wind resource and energy yield estimates for offshore wind farm sites.

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1 INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

1.1 INTRODUCTION

There is a need for a standardised method to model the vertical wind profile offshore. A number of methods are used in the literature to calculate the Obukhov Length which is only valid in stationary, homogeneous conditions. Monin-Obukhov theory is also confined to the surface layer where turbulent fluxes can be considered to remain constant. Wind speed extrapolations usually produce higher deviations to observed wind speeds in stable conditions due to the reduced boundary height and the stability limit range in which the flux profile equations are valid. The formation of internal boundary layers further limits the applicability of M-O theory near the coastal discontinuity.

As a result, there is a need to examine the applicability of the diabatic wind profile in wind speed extrapolations. A standardised method needs to be identified in order to convince wind farm developers that it is worthwhile to consider the thermal stratification of the atmosphere in wind resource assessments.

2 OUTLINE OF WORK CARRIED OUT

2.1 SETUP

The site studied is a coastal location on the western coastline of Norway close to the village of Titran on the island of Frøya at the mouth of the fjord of Trondheim (see Figure 1). Two 100m meteorological masts and one 45m mast were installed at the Skipheia station approximately 300m inland from the southern coastline of Frøya. These installations were provided as part of the Norwegian Research Centre for Offshore Wind Technology (NOWITECH) initiative. Access to the data was acquired through MARINET.

Figure 1: Illustration of the location of the NTNU measurement station [credit: Lars Saetran]

2.2 TESTS

Measurements from one of the 100m meteorological masts (Fig. 2) at Skipheia station was provided for the period from 18th November 2009 to 30th June 2011. The mast is composed of steel framework. Two ultrasonic anemometers and one temperature sensor are mounted at each level (10m, 16m, 25m, 40m, 70m and 100m). The ultrasonic anemometers are located on 2.5m long booms, orientated at 180° to each other in order to eliminate mast distortion effects. The ultrasonic anemometers used are *WindObserver II Wind Speed Sensors*, manufactured by Gill Instruments. However, these 2D anemometers only provide wind speed measurements in the horizontal plane at a frequency of 1 Hz. Therefore, direct estimates of vertical momentum and heat fluxes could not be obtained. An instrumentation house is located nearby, housing the Data Acquisition System.

Figure 2: Meteorological mast at NTNU [source: Lars Saetran, NTNU]

1.1.1 Sorting the Data

As the required high frequency measurements were not available, the data was sorted into 10 minute time-averaged intervals for wind speed, wind direction and temperature. The temperature at each level was converted to potential temperature using the dry adiabatic lapse rate described previously as there were no measurements of relative humidity recorded. The anemometers on the mast are orientated such that true north is located at a wind angle of 139° relative to the anemometers 'north'. Therefore the wind direction values were converted to the standard co-ordinate system, with 0° representing true north. In order to

eliminate mast distortion effects, the data was sorted into directional bins with an angle width of 15°. The wind speed measurements from the south-eastern sensors (1) and north-western (2) were compared to locate the regions where mast shadow effects were present. The results are illustrated in Figure 3 with the south eastern sensors showing clear mast shadow effect for wind directions coming from the north-west. Therefore, wind speeds from the south eastern sensors were used for wind directions between 45-225° with the north western sensors wind speed readings used for wind directions between 225-45°.

Figure 2: Average ratio of wind speeds from sensor 1 and sensor 2 at each level at the 100m NTNU mast

1.2 ADDITIONAL SATELLITE DATA

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) provide satellite measurements of the sea surface temperature (SST) across the entire globe. One set of readings they provide is referred to as Real Time Global (RTG) data. The daily sea surface temperature product is freely accessible online at [1]. The spatial resolution is a 1/12 degree (latitude and longitude) grid with a frequency of one reading per day. The value recorded is an averaged SST value within each grid box and is obtained via a two-dimensional variational interpolation analysis of the most recent 24-hours buoy and ship data, satellite retrieved SST data, and SST's derived from satellite-observed sea-ice coverage. As the measurements from satellites generally obtain skin temperatures (\approx top 10 microns of the water surface), it is recommended to cool the RTG value by 0.17K.

1.3 SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE FORMULATIONS

An accurate prediction of the sea surface temperature offshore is crucial in an atmospheric stability analysis. However, this parameter is very difficult to measure. In many cases, bulk water temperatures (recorded at a depth below sea level) are used. ECMWF reanalysis data and satellite measurements provide other alternatives. Although the meteorological mast at NTNU is located on land, the wind is likely to be influenced by the Norwegian Sea for westerly wind directions. Therefore another RTG dataset was generated for SST values using the grid coordinate at 63.65°N, 8.34°E.

2.0 ANALYSIS – NTNU (COASTAL SITE)

The study begins with a preliminary analysis on the wind resource. The rest of the chapter focuses on wind extrapolation techniques and whether the techniques used at previously-studied offshore sites are valid in such a complex coastal environment.

2.1 PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS – GENERAL WIND RESOURCE

2.1.1 Average Wind Speed

The average wind speed at four measurement heights for each three month interval can be seen in Figure 4. The overall average wind speed at a height of 70m from 18th November 2009 to 30th June 2011 is 7.85m/s, which is noticeably lower than the corresponding values at offshore sites Egmond aan Zee (OWEZ) and FINO 1. Wind speeds are highest in the winter months.

Figure 4: Average wind speeds at each height per month at NTNU. 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011

2.1.2 Wind Distribution

The wind distribution at the site is illustrated in Figure 5 and is based on measurements at 70m. The predominant wind direction is from the south west. However, a substantial portion of wind also comes from the east. The highest wind speeds come from the south west; the wind sector containing the clearest overwater fetch. This reinforces the suggestion that there are higher wind speeds offshore than on land.

Figure 5: Wind Rose plot based on 70m measurements at the NTNU site from 18th November 2009 to 30th June 2011

2.1.3 Shear Coefficient

The shear coefficient (α) is computed for each 10 minute time interval at NTNU using the same procedures as before. The measurements at 10m, 25m, 40m and 70m are used in this analysis. The averaged values for each 15° degree directional bin are shown in Figure 6. The values obtained are similar to those found in a previous study of the FINO 1 offshore mast which is understandable given the site at Titran is a small island surrounded by water with long overseas fetches to the south west, west and north. There are slightly larger values obtained for α for winds blowing from the east and south east where the coastline of Norway is in close proximity.

Figure 6: Plot of Shear coefficient versus Wind Direction at NTNU, 18th November 2009 – 30th June 2011

2.2 MODELLING THE VERTICAL WIND PROFILE

This section investigates the applicability of various wind speed extrapolation techniques in a coastal environment. Monin-Obukhov theory is only valid in homogeneous stationary conditions. The NTNU mast is located on land close to the shoreline in a region that is expected to have non homogeneous conditions. Therefore, one would expect the extrapolation procedures used previously to be inapplicable in such an environment. The Bulk method refers to the Bulk Richardson calculation described by Grachev and Fairall [2]. Wind speeds are extrapolated from a number of lower measurement heights to the 70m measurement height. The Obukhov Length is calculated using the bulk method and the combined air method. RTG satellite data is used to estimate the SST. As the site is located on land but surrounded by a marine environment, two values for the sea surface roughness are evaluated; $z_0 = 0.0002\text{m}$ (ocean) and $z_0 = 0.01\text{m}$ (typical for rough pasture). Corrupted data as well as measured wind speeds $< 4\text{m/s}$ at 70m are eliminated.

It was decided to split the analysis into three wind sectors as illustrated in Figure 7. The first sector lies between $180\text{-}270^\circ$ and is considered to be a long marine fetch. Within this zone, the mast is approximately 300-400m from the coastline. Therefore it is anticipated that potential internal boundary layers (IBLs) will not have increased in height beyond the measurement heights of the mast. The second region analysed contains winds blowing from $45\text{-}180^\circ$. This is considered a mixed land and marine fetch as the wind flows over land and sea within this fetch. Finally, the last sector that will be examined lies between $270\text{-}45^\circ$. This region contains land fetches in excess of 2km preceded by a long marine fetch. However, in contrast to the $180\text{-}270^\circ$ wind sector, IBL heights are expected to be at similar levels to the lower measurement heights on the mast at NTNU.

Figure 7: Illustration of the wind sectors used at NTNU

2.2.1 Long Marine Fetch (180-270°)

In order to obtain an idea of what surface roughness value to use for this wind sector, a preliminary analysis using solely the neutral profile is undertaken. Wind speeds are extrapolated from 10m, 16m and 25m up to an elevation of 70m using values of 0.0002m and 0.01m for the surface roughness. Figure 8 illustrates the results obtained for the entire study period. In each case, the offshore value of 0.0002m produces lower RMSE values than the corresponding results for the land surface roughness value. This suggests that for this wind sector, the wind is still primarily influenced by the preceding overwater fetch. This is to be expected as the mast is within 300-400m of the coastline and the wind flow could not have adjusted to the new surface roughness. Therefore, it is decided to proceed with z_0 equal to 0.0002m for this wind sector. Another interesting point to note is that the choice of reference height (10m, 16m or 25m) is a more significant influence on the extrapolated wind speed than the value of z_0 .

Figure 8: (a) RMSE values for predicted wind speeds at 70m using the neutral profile at a number of heights at NTNU, all conditions, 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011, sector 180-270°.

2.2.1.1 Extrapolating from 10m measurement

Figure 9 shows the results obtained for wind speed extrapolations from the 10m measurement height up to 70m. In the diagram, 'Bulk-SST' denotes the bulk method utilising the SST as the surface temperature and similarly, 'Bulk-Land' represents the bulk method with the measurement at the land surface on the mast used as the surface temperature. Throughout the period, the diabatic profile using the SST reduces the magnitude of RMSE values compared to the other techniques. This suggests that despite the mast being located on land, the VWP can still be modelled using the extrapolation techniques previously used in the MABL. However, unlike in the other sites, the predicted average wind speed is not as consistent as desired. The RMSE values are also higher than the other sites' results and as a result it may be necessary to extrapolate from higher elevations.

Figure 9: (a) RMSE values and (b) differences in average predicted wind speeds (m/s) at 70m using 10m measurement height and $z_0 = 0.0002\text{m}$ at NTNU, all conditions, 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011, sector 180-270°.

2.2.1.2 Extrapolating from 16m measurement

Figure 10 illustrates the results for the same analysis as before except the 16m measurement height is used instead of the 10m readings. The combined air method is also included using the measurements at 10m and 16m. Once again, there is an improvement using the diabatic profile with lower RMSE values than the neutral profile. The use of the SST appears to be more advisable than the land temperature again for this fetch. This is also our first chance to see the air method used with lower measurement heights. The results show improvements compared to the neutral profile, however it does have higher RMSE errors than the bulk method. The distance between the 10m and 16m measurements heights is small; however, there is a larger change in wind speeds between these heights than in the case studied for FINO 1 (33m-40m). The average wind speed prediction is still not as consistent over time as one would hope for, although the bulk method does reduce the deviations from the observed values compared to the neutral profile.

Figure 10: (a) RMSE values and (b) differences in average predicted wind speeds (m/s) at 70m using 16m measurement height and $z_0 = 0.0002\text{m}$ at NTNU, all conditions, 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011, sector 180-270°.

Figure 11: Average Potential Temperature Profile at NTNU over the entire study period

2.2.2 Mixed Land and Marine Fetch (45-180°)

The next wind sector to be investigated comprises wind blowing from between 45-180°. The fetch contains a mixture of land and sea fetch which is likely to cause a large degree of irregularity in the wind flow and surface fluxes. Therefore, there is uncertainty whether to use a sea surface roughness of 0.0002m or land value of 0.01m for z_0 .

A comparison is made between wind speed predictions using the neutral profile and readings at 10m, 16m, and 25m. The results in Figure 12 show a large variation in the magnitude of deviations from observed wind speeds at 70m using both surface roughness (z_0) values. Unlike the previous section, there is no obvious value to be taken for z_0 . As a result, it is decided to use both 0.0002m and 0.01m for z_0 for the rest of this analysis. It is anticipated that both roughness values have a large influence on the vertical wind profile (VWP). The model suggested by Floors [3] is likely to be more accurate. However, the extremely variable fetch type is also going to hinder such a procedure with a large degree of certainty over the upstream roughness value.

Figure 12: (a) RMSE values for predicted wind speeds at 70m using the neutral profile at a number of heights at NTNU, all conditions, 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011, sector 45-180°.

2.2.3 Land Fetch > 2km preceded by Long Marine Fetch

The final sector to be analysed consists of a land fetch between 2km and 3km in length, preceded by long overwater fetch. A comparison of wind speed extrapolations from the lower measurement heights up to 70m using the neutral profile is shown in Figure 13. Once again, there is ambiguity over the most appropriate surface roughness value to use. The RMSE values for each measurement height are lower than the mixed fetch in the previous section. An assumption of z_0 equal to 0.0002m appears to lead to underestimations of the wind speed at 70m, while a value of 0.01m appears to overestimate the wind speed at this elevation.

The model suggested by Floors [2], is likely to be more accurate in this scenario as there is a uniform ocean fetch upstream of the coastal discontinuity. The presence of internal boundary layers is expected to cause errors in the extrapolation techniques used throughout the project. However, as the distance to the

coastline is not that large in this wind sector, it is decided to test out the methods used previously. Therefore, the values 0.0002m and 0.01m will continue to be compared for this analysis.

Figure 13: (a) RMSE values for predicted wind speeds at 70m using the neutral profile at a number of heights at NTNU, all conditions, 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011. Sector 270-45°

Wind speeds are extrapolated from 10m, 16m, 25m and 40m up to 70m using various methods to calculate L and z_0 as in sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. The results over the entire period are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: RMSE values (m/s) of predicted wind speeds at 70m at NTNU, 18 November 2009 – 30 June 2011, wind sector 270-45°.

RMSE (m/s) Predicted vs. Observed Wind Speeds @70m			
Extrapolation heights	Method to calculate L	z0 = 0.0002m	z0 = 0.01m
10m → 70m	Neutral	0.95	0.94
	Bulk (SST)	1.33	1.41
	Bulk (Land)	0.87	0.91
16m → 70m	Neutral	0.83	0.79
	Bulk (SST)	1.09	1.14
	Bulk (Land)	0.74	0.75
	Air-Air (10-16m)	0.71	0.84
25m → 70m	Neutral	0.69	0.61
	Bulk (SST)	0.79	0.76
	Bulk (Land)	0.60	0.64
	Air-Air (16-25m)	0.84	1.08
40m → 70m	Neutral	0.47	0.40
	Bulk (SST)	0.52	0.49
	Bulk (Land)	0.53	0.51
	Air-Air (10-40m)	0.45	0.41
	Air-Air (16-40m)	0.47	0.41
	Air-Air (25-40m)	0.55	0.50

Table 1 does not indicate which technique is the most reliable to use to extrapolate wind speeds in this wind sector. An interesting point to note is that the air-air method produces lower RMSE values than the bulk method for wind speed extrapolations from 16m up to 70m. The wind flow at 70m for this wind sector is likely to be in a layer which remains in equilibrium with the overwater fetch. In the case of the bulk method, the use of land surface roughnesses and temperatures are unlikely to accurately model the VWP in this region. Furthermore, the use of the SST as the surface temperature appears to produce higher deviations in extrapolated wind speeds using the bulk method than the land temperature. The air method shows potential without improving the prediction from the neutral profile significantly.

The results give no clear indication of the correct surface roughness value to use as outlined previously. Deviations in extrapolated wind speeds from 25m and 40m using the bulk method, sea surface roughness and temperature values begin to decrease in comparison to the previous two reference heights. This suggests that the 25m height is entering into the transition layer described by Floors [2] where the wind flow is adjusting from the ocean surface effects to the land cover effects. Nonetheless, the diabatic profile continues to provide no improvement to the VWP in this wind sector. Once again, the air method performs poorly using the 25m temperature measurements.

The wind speed extrapolations from the 40m measurement height to 70m in this wind sector provide the final use of the aforementioned techniques in this study. Yet again, the use of the 40m readings produces the lowest RMSE errors for the wind speed predictions at 70m. The diabatic wind profile has not significantly improved the VWP in this wind sector.

As with the mixed fetch, the installation of a LIDAR device is recommended to acquire an accurate model of the VWP at a coastal location similar to the surroundings of the NTNU mast. An alternative is the development of a model similar to that produced by Floors [3]. Floors model focuses solely on neutral conditions. The height of the IBL is likely to grow faster in unstable conditions due to enhanced mixing in the air. Therefore, there is potential for future analysis in implementing an atmospheric stability term into Floors model. Unfortunately, due to time constraints this could not be done in this project.

3 MAIN LEARNING OUTCOMES

3.1 CONCLUSION/DISCUSSION

The NTNU mast provided meteorological data from a coastal environment with differing wind flow regimes to those experienced at other offshore sites studied (Egmond aan Zee and FINO1). It was found that the average wind speeds at the coastal location are lower than those at the offshore sites. Despite, the mast being located on land close to the coastline, the bulk method again performs well for the wind sector containing long overseas fetch using sea surface roughness and temperatures. The diabatic profile improves the VWP prediction in comparison to the neutral profile suggesting that the wind flow regime is predominantly influenced by the marine boundary layer. The air methods also show potential to calculate L, although the use of the 25m temperature readings appeared to cause errors.

As expected, the diabatic profile and more precisely M-O theory performs poorly in the other wind sectors. The mixed fetch to the south east of the mast creates a large degree of complexity in the wind flow regime in this region. The diabatic profile produces large errors with uncertainty over an appropriate value to use for the surface roughness. It may prove difficult to acquire planning for the installation of a 100m meteorological mast at coastal locations. Therefore, it is recommended to install a LIDAR device to acquire an accurate model of the VWP for this fetch type. Should it be necessary to extrapolate wind speeds from lower elevations to the relevant heights, the use of a computational fluid dynamics model is recommended given the irregularities in the surfaces over which the wind flows.

Finally, a wind sector containing a land fetch in excess of 2km preceded by long overwater fetch was analysed. Once again, the diabatic profile performed poorly in this region due to the presence of internal boundary layers. It remains unclear whether to model the wind using offshore or onshore parameter values. In fact, it is anticipated that the wind flow is influenced by a combination of both surfaces. The lower measurements at 10m and 16m are likely to be located at heights in equilibrium with the land surface. However, the wind flow at 70m is still expected to be primarily influenced by the sea surface. Therefore, the development of a model similar to that suggested by Floors [3] is recommended, with the inclusion of an atmospheric stability correction term to estimate the growth of the internal boundary layer height downstream of the coastal discontinuity. Nonetheless, it is still suggested to install a LIDAR device to acquire a thorough understanding of the variations in wind shear at such a location.

3.2 KEY LESSONS LEARNED

- The analysis of the NTNU data also questions the installation of a meteorological mast or any measurement device on land close to shore as part of a wind resource assessment for a site located 20-30km offshore. The wind flow regimes have been shown to be very different in each environment.
- It is strongly recommended to install in-situ measuring devices at the location of the proposed wind farm to acquire a true representation of the wind resource in the region. It may be impractical to install LIDAR devices or tall meteorological masts in such locations.
- Therefore the installation of smaller masts will enable the techniques used throughout this research to attain accurate predictions of the wind speeds at turbine hub heights and throughout the rotor area.

4 FURTHER INFORMATION

4.1 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

- Coffey, K. and McKeogh, E. and Leahy, P. Is there a value in including atmospheric stability in wind resource assessments in the marine environment? International Conference on Energy & Meteorology, Toulouse, June 2013.
- Coffey, K. Atmospheric Stability and Coastal Effects on Nearshore and Offshore Wind Energy Resources. M.Eng.Sc. Thesis, University College Cork, 2013.

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